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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The investment behind the BEACONING project requires tangible and perceivable results, and this Dissemination and Communication plan provides the BEACONING strategy to support all project partners in obtaining and maximizing this impact.

The document stems from the draft plan initially provided in the Description of Action (DoA) of the proposal, and extends it with specific actions and Key Performance Indicators (KPI) that will serve as a benchmark for the dissemination impact of the BEACONING project.

This is a live document that will be periodically updated and completed throughout the BEACONING project lifecycle, reflecting best practices and lessons learnt during the execution of the project in a flexible and proactive way, so that they can spread to the whole consortium.

The objective of this document is to describe the guidelines and the action plan that will further the main project goals of impact and dissemination. It also articulates how those goals will be achieved and the teams responsible for carrying out each proposed activity.

1 INTRODUCTION

The BEACONING project requires tangible and perceivable results, therefore this Dissemination and Communication plan provides the BEACONING strategy to maximize this impact. In particular, the strategy contemplates five main objectives, and offers different actions and expectations in order to achieve them:

1. **Increase awareness**, understanding and action towards project objectives, activities and results through continuous, multi-channel, multilingual dissemination targeting all relevant stakeholders. In this case, the key stakeholders are educational institutions, TEL developers and educational authorities.
2. **Contribute to the advancement of BEACONING R&D** and the implementation of solutions by engaging discussions and encouraging collaborations within and between the scientific community, end-users and industry.
3. **Promote open access** of and **stimulate interest** in the BEACONING platform in practice, by active testing or participation.
4. **Promote the adoption of the project outcomes** during the project implementation and beyond by identified stakeholder groups in the education, training and lifelong learning sector, including professionals, instructors, teacher trainers, the software industry, and more.
5. **Inform decision and policy makers in education** on the added value of a ubiquitous learning platform by providing insights on the project and by evaluating outcomes in real life settings.

We aim to achieve these objectives through a three-tiered approach, where relevant stakeholders are increasingly engaged.

- Tier 1 actions promote awareness;
- Tier 2 actions provide understanding of the project; and
- Tier 3 actions promote specific actions to adopt and leverage the project's results.

1.1 ROLE OF THIS DELIVERABLE IN THE PROJECT

This deliverable provides the Dissemination and Communication plan for the BEACONING project. It represents a shared vision of how the project's goals and results will be communicated to different stakeholders and target audiences, and it serves as a reference for all partners in their involvement in dissemination and communication activities.

This document will also serve as a plan to evaluate how the project is progressing along the execution of the project and to identify early both best practices that should be generalized or open issues about the dissemination (e.g. specific stakeholders not being reached) and what corrective actions should be taken to address those issues.

1.2 APPROACH

This document has been prepared following and extending the guidelines set in the BEACONING DoA, and improved through different sources of input:

- Literature analysis on dissemination and communication approaches;
- A special brainstorming session during the BEACONING Kick-off Meeting;
- Experience from previous international projects, including former FP6/FP7 projects and ongoing H2020 projects (e.g. RAGE) and Erasmus+ projects;
- Internal peer reviews of the document and the proposed strategies.

The approach is to create a ***shared understanding*** inside the project’s rich, large and diverse consortium on how to best leverage our significant combined experience, expertise and project-derived assets to maximize our impact.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The deliverable is structured as follows:

Section 2 provides a detailed explanation of the five objectives and the three-tiered approach.

Section 3 identifies the main target audiences for dissemination, as well as the specific type of activities that would be relevant for engaging each audience at each tier.

Section 4 describes in detail the different dissemination actions and project activities that will be applied as part of this Dissemination and Communication Plan.

Section 5 sets the Key Performance Indicators to benchmark the impact of this Dissemination and Communication Plan.

2 GENERAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

The overall goal of the BEACONING project is to help open up education through pilots for a digital learning platform that blends physical and digital learning spaces, merging formal, non-formal and informal learning contexts that enables *all* learners (abled and disabled) to equally access the same learning opportunities, and to gain highly contextualized, connected and personalised experiences beyond the barriers of temporal and physical classrooms. This will create a social space that connects researchers, gaming industries, intermediaries, education providers, policy makers and end-users.

BEACONING's success largely depends on achieving a productive communication beyond the consortium's frontiers. This will enable the Expected Impacts that drive the design and execution of the project. Unless the Consortium, as a whole, convinces third parties to use the results of the project, BEACONING could be seen as a failure.

In the medium and long term, the aim of this plan is to create and nurture the core of an ecosystem that will guarantee sustainability and adoption of project results in real contexts.

As shown in the DoA, BEACONING aims to communicate and broaden its impact, and seeks for both research partners and SMEs a return on investment and a concrete commercial exploitation possibility. Exploitation activities are also intended to bolster the serious games market in general and to make the activity of designing and selling serious games more advantageous for all involved stakeholders. The target audience will be as broad as possible, with a focus on both academia and industry. As education is mostly a regulated sector, BEACONING also needs to address and appeal to educational authorities.

Finally, this plan also aims to disseminate across Europe the impact that these achievements can have for European citizens, with special attention to how this affects the employability of our future workforce. This will also include technological awareness to optimize exploitation and impact.

2.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this plan is to increase the visibility of the project and to ensure that the outcomes of the project previously described have a significant impact across Europe.

This general objective of impact must be translated into more specific objectives, which will be progressively activated as the project advances. In particular, we expect to focus on the five specific objectives as already described in the background section.

Initially, dissemination will focus on increasing awareness (see Table 1). Later, it will seek a deeper engagement by stakeholders. This approach also takes into account that some of the tasks, such as research, will require more time to achieve the first results, since the usual dissemination channel for this goal is by participating in conferences and publications, which require long cycles of experimentation, validation and writing, and peer review before actual dissemination in journals and specialized conferences can take place.

	M01- M09	M10- M18	M18- M27	M28- M36
Increase awareness Making potential stakeholders aware of the project's activities and outcomes				
Advancement R&D Encouraging collaboration among scientific community, industry and users.				
Open Access To stimulate BEACONING use by potential stakeholders				
Outcomes adoption To promote uptake of BEACONING's results in the educational sector, software industry, etc.				
Inform decision-makers. Promoting the added value of BEACONING platform.				

Table 1. Progressive activation of BEACONING's dissemination objectives

2.2 THREE-TIERED DISSEMINATION APPROACH

The BEACONING communication plan should provide mechanisms for timely access and appropriate distribution of project information to all targeted stakeholders. We are aware that to achieve an influence on someone (impact), a clear vision of the impact we aim to generate should be defined, along with a coherent definition and interaction of target groups, messages and channels to accelerate our path from awareness to impact.

To achieve that impact, as described in the previous section, dissemination is three-tiered:

- i) *Awareness*
- ii) *Understanding*
- iii) *Action*

Specific materials will be elaborated in each tier and by targeted stakeholders. The main channel will be the BEACONING portal (described in D2.2), which is dynamically updated, gamified and used as the main information repository for the project and dissemination of news. This portal will provide access to the BEACONING ecosystem and Work Environment. The different communities will be targeted through different channels. This three-level approach is divided by the main focus of activities:

Tier 1: Promote awareness

Raising awareness is where the road to dissemination starts. Awareness will remain important throughout the project's lifecycle. Its main goal is to raise project visibility by communicating the most relevant project activities, benefits and outcomes through channels with wide reach (e.g. website, social networks, conferences, press releases, dissemination materials, etc.)

Tier 2: Promote understanding of the project

This tier will focus on further dissemination of project outcomes and benefits to identified target groups through the appropriate communication channels (e.g. key networks, workshops, meetings). Describing use-cases and specific scenarios will be one of the elements used to make the project's benefits both concrete and understandable.

Tier 3: Promote specific actions to adopt and leverage the project's results

Proactive actions to drive project result adoption, such as focus group participation, by communicating benefit/opportunity oriented messages to target groups through pertinent channels (e.g. key networks, workshops, focus groups). Furthermore, it should influence educational stakeholders' uptake of BEACONING outcomes through benefit/opportunity oriented messages.

2.3 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TEAM

To deal with the complexities of a project with many partners, spread among multiple countries, and with deployment planned in multiple heterogeneous locations, we propose a mixed top-down and bottom-up approach.

WP2 and the project coordinator leaders will lead the general dissemination activities, oversee reporting on communication and dissemination activities by partners, and ensure that all partners understand that this task is a shared goal where they should participate (*top-down approach*).

However, we consider that partners, as recognized experts in their fields, have very valuable knowledge of their own countries and industries. Therefore, we will rely on them to propose local, regional or country-specific activities. This will improve impact when reaching national stakeholders, as communication will be in their own language and taking fully into account each partner's localized knowledge (*bottom-up approach*).

We will also promote that partners in the same country cooperate actively to achieve a larger impact (e.g. France as an example with several partners from different industries). The WP2 leader and the coordinator will identify which of these activities are the most successful and will propose these successes to the rest of the consortium for analysis, eventual adoption and replication in each partner's specific cases (*horizontal approach*).

To articulate these efforts, each partner will nominate a person responsible for communication and dissemination that will be in charge of carrying out the activities promoted by the consortium, and will report specific actions promoted by their partner to the consortium (both alone or in collaboration with other local partners).

2.4 LANGUAGE

The main dissemination language will be English.

However, the project seeks to achieve the greatest possible impact in multiple countries, which also requires an internationalization effort. The project will rely on each partner for decision about the localization of the main dissemination materials, including specific language to use, and even the possible adaptation of materials for local requirements (see D2.2). This will apply,

for instance, to the translation and localization of the general press releases and the main dissemination materials.

Each partner will be responsible for creating the dissemination contents for their specific cases or countries. However, the project will keep an archive of all partners' materials, both for accountability and to make them available to other project partners.

3 TARGET AUDIENCES

To ensure a successful adoption of BEACONING’s results, the focus of the project’s dissemination and communication efforts will target the entire Educational Value Chain.

The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) articulates action channels ranging from participation and organization of events to direct contact, mass-media, online presence and active stakeholder engagement.

We consider industry, research and end-users as key stakeholder groups, in order to guarantee maximum impact, specific dissemination plans will be developed for each of these groups. The dissemination partners and stakeholders will be actively involved in the validation of the specific dissemination plans and activities.

The BEACONING DoA already presented an in-depth analysis of specific dissemination activities targeting different types of stakeholders. The table below shows the dissemination plan according to the different stakeholders (see Table 2).

Target Community	Dissemination
Educational Technology and Gaming Industry and commerce	<p>Focus on the benefits to be gained by industry and commerce becoming active agents of testing and developing the BEACONING solution, i.e. industry associations/ chambers of commerce, business support/ promotion organizations, identified initiative organizations specific to each region.</p> <p>We will exploit the wide networks of the partners, such as the EdTech partners – SEBIT, SIVECO, ATS, ORT, Gaming – SUCCUBUS, IMA, GEOMOTION, PLAYSOFT and enabling technologies – HFC and IFINITY.</p>
Scientific and Research community	<p>Disseminating the innovation methodology.</p> <p>Focus on links and synergies with other regions and regional actors. The living labs (LL) under ENOLL will also be capitalised on. COVUNI and BIBA are part of a LL under ENOLL. ORT, ATS and SIVECO will have access to Microsoft Education and the associate partners will also provide global outreach that is pushing EdTechs into schools. We will identify what of those initiative are more successful to extend and replicate them in other countries.</p> <p>UCM will promote the results in the NoE eMadrid that articulates the research in e-learning and ICT in education in the Madrid region. We will reuse the previous formal and informal networks created in other EU projects (e.g. NoE GALA) where some of the project partners participated.</p>
Local / regional authorities / companies, public-private partnerships, decisions and policy makers, European Commission	<p>Dissemination will focus on developing contacts in these organizations, encouraging them to engage in BEACONING, and raising awareness on the benefit of including BEACONING in service provision.</p>
Fes, HEs, VETs, NGOs, recruitment, employers, businesses, charities, existing networks	<p>Focus on European institutions, including the DGs and on other European regional representative bodies. The strategy for these other representative bodies is to identify national specific issues. This will allow regional and European actors to engage together on specific BEACONING themes, thus multiplying their efforts and impact.</p>

Table 2. Target audiences and key messages

The afore-mentioned groups will be approached to make them aware of the project to ensure they understand its concept, technical background, benefits and usage, among others. It is crucial for BEACONING to engage with the target groups that will potentially adopt the project's results. Therefore, the engagement accomplished with adopters in institutional sectors as well as policy makers are highly relevant.

The timing of this activities will be carried out according to the general plan established in Table 1. That means that the initial tasks for increasing awareness should be completed by month 9 and later on maintained along the duration of the project. Similar timing will be applied for the other tiers and activities.

Due to the diversity of the European educational landscape and to the multilingualism and cultural aspects, each partner will be responsible for identifying and approaching relevant stakeholder at their locations (regions and countries). They will be supported in this task both by the WP2 leader and by the project coordinator.

4 DETAILED DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

The aforementioned target audiences are diverse in nature, and therefore should be approached through different channels and activities.

The core of the BEACONING project blends technical and learning innovation. To construct the innovative approach, we foresee both online and offline communication channels such as face-to-face meetings, remote meetings, events, as well as using a wide social media and academic communication strategy to better reach the project target groups.

The most appropriate channels have been selected to reach each target audience according to: 1) audiences' profile, 2) the message we want to convey, and 3) to the level of interaction we would like to obtain. The identified dissemination channels used to reach each target group are detailed in the table below:

Target Community	Activities
Educational Technology and Gaming Industry and commerce	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyers, brochures Broadcast/Press Magazines • Scientific papers • Project Website • Social media • Community Building • Workshops, exhibit • Participation in Learning Labs • Promotional videos
Scientific and Research community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentations • Workshops • Contact with related EU projects • Project Website • Social media • Newsletters • Lectures • Community Building • Workshops • Participation in Learning Labs
Local / regional authorities / companies, public-private partnerships, decisions and policy makers, European Commission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commissioning briefing doc • Press/broadcast • "On-site" visits • Brochures • Seminars/workshops • Project Website • Social media • Promotional videos
Fes, HEs, VETs, NGOs, recruitment, employers, businesses, charities, existing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Website • Social media • Press/Broadcast • Brochures • Conferences, seminars, workshops • Existing events of the stakeholders • Participation in Learning Labs • Promotional videos

Table 3. Specific actions targeting each audience group

All these actions –with their focus and detailed approaches– are described in the following subsections.

4.1 DIGITAL COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Project website

Project's website has already been implemented and can be accessed through <http://www.beaconing.eu/>. The main goal of the website is to raise awareness regarding BEACONING's activities, as well as promoting engagement from targeted stakeholder communities.

The website is the main information platform where intermediate and final project outcomes, reports, news and publications are made available and updated. Furthermore, it promotes interaction among different groups by publishing events and project documents. The selected CMS is Wordpress, which provides a publishing platform, a blog tool, and integration with Twitter, LinkedIn and Google+ among others. The website should become a reference for innovative use of games in education, providing both quality content (e.g. blog posts) and up-to-date information on events, including those organized by BEACONING and third parties.

According to recently promoted EU practices and regulations all project publications (i.e. papers, reports, etc.) will be accessible through the website, and will either be directly hosted in the same website or at a central open repository.

Regular Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) analysis will be performed to identify keywords for the project and optimize metadata, URLs, HTML code, and internal link structure (among other criteria) to maximize project visibility.

A full description of the BEACONING website can be found at the deliverable D2.2 Project branding and website start-up.

Social media

Social media will enhance online visibility of the project, and will multiply the communication efforts of the partners. Besides, presence and activity in social networks will improve the project's positioning through engine search, image search, local search, etc.

BEACONING presence in social networks:

- **Twitter:** <https://twitter.com/BeaconingEU>
- **Facebook:** <https://www.facebook.com/beaconing/>
- **Blog:** <http://www.beaconing.eu/>
- **YouTube:** https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCgPA_DsSPppbq_Yzu39OnNA

Social media presence will create informal links and cross-fertilization with other communities and projects building on some of the pre-existing channels already used or even managed by some of the project members.

For instance, BEACONING can profit from the pre-existing games-related groups from previous EU projects such as the EU LLP SEGAN project (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/segan/> with more than 800 members) and the Serious Games Society page developed within the GALA Network-of-Excellence (<https://www.facebook.com/SeriousGamesSociety/>, with over 700 members). These will also be important venues for social media publishing, and some of the information published there by third parties will be also curated and shared using BEACONING's social media channels.

In addition to classical social networks, since the project will generate lots of static content (papers, public deliverables, presentations and dissemination materials) which rarely allows social media interaction, we will endeavour to convert static content into dynamic content by sharing it within web 2.0 tools to increase visibility.

For the promotion of academic writings, we have created a **ResearchGate page** for papers and presentations:

https://www.researchgate.net/project/BEACONING_5739cbc693553bec4a64ecb9

We also plan to be active in **SlideShare**, which has a more diverse demographic (e.g. industry) than ResearchGate. Instead of creating a SlideShare account for the project we will promote the publication of all presentations directly or partially related with BEACONING in partners' currently existing personal accounts. This will allow for a better identification of partners within the project and, at the same time, reuse the pre-existing channel that could help into reaching a wider audience. We also plan to be active in **LinkedIn** but due to the industrial orientation and to the high number of existing groups in related topics (e.g. elearning, games, gamification, etc) we plan to be active initially in some of the pre-existing groups.

Partners' social networks will constitute key platforms to disseminate BEACONING activities. We will promote actively that partners rely not only on their own social network accounts, but also use their institutional accounts to obtain a greater impact. For instance, the Computense University's Twitter account (@unicomplutense) already has over 50000 followers, including some of the most influential media in Spain and South America.

Newsletters

Written reports will present the information and the news to all the BEACONING partners. It is important to note that the frequency of the emails will be carefully planned so not to overwhelm the recipients.

The initial frequency will be **quarterly** (starting in M6), and mailings will be supervised by the project coordinator (later in the project we will analyse if this frequency should be modified). Each issue will gather contributions from the partners and will reflect the main achievements in the project (mailings will also be coordinated with press releases and other dissemination materials).

4.2 ACADEMIC ACTIVITIES

Scientific papers

Since the project integrates contributions from different scientific disciplines and covert technological issues addressed to the industry such as business models and technology acceptance matters, many journals could be targeted for BEACONING's topics. A list of possible high-impact target journals and sites includes:

- Computers In Education
- IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies
- International Journal of Game-Based Learning
- The International Journal of Gaming and Computer-Mediated Simulations
- International Journal of Computer Games Technology
- IEEE Transactions on Computational Intelligence and AI in Games
- Simulations & Gaming
- Computers In Human Behaviour
- International Journal of Serious Games
- Gamasutra

- GameDev.net
- Develop
- Inside social games

Scientific papers will also be submitted at scientific seminars and workshops (listed in the next section).

WP2 and the project coordinator will actively promote the production of joint publications with the project's results. Every three months the Communication and Dissemination Team will be contacted to analyse possibilities for joint publications and to select the best venues for those publications.

Conferences, seminars, workshops

The project integrates contributions from different scientific disciplines and will participate and/or organise scientific seminars, conferences and workshops to disseminate concepts and ideas of BEACONING giving a solid overview of the project.

All partners will periodically evaluate event participation based on interest and importance for the project, potential impact, audience and availability. Different kind of conferences have been considered covering the different aspects of the projects (i.e., academic, industrial, educational) and the different kind of stakeholders (i.e. research centers, enterprises).

A calendar of relevant events, as detailed in the table below (see Table 4), will be made available to project partners to support the coordination and organisation of partners' attendance and dissemination efforts. The table below is given as an example of possible targets for the partner's research papers. It describes events identified by the consortium so far (last updated on 30th June, 2016).

Title	Date	Location	URL
DIGRA-FDG	1-6 August 2016	Dundee, Scotland, UK	http://www.digra.org/
Game Developers Conference (or GDC Europe)	14-18 Mar 2016	San Francisco, California	http://www.gdconf.com/
ACM CHI	7-12 May 2016	San Jose, CA	http://chi2016.acm.org
AIED (Artificial Intelligence in Education)	2017 (to be determined)	Philippines	http://iaied.org
Brains Eden Gaming Festival	24-27 Jun 2016	Cambridge, UK	http://www.brainseden.net/
ICALT (International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies)	24-25 Oct 2016	Paris, France	https://www.waset.org/conference/2016/10/paris/ICALT
IEEE ICALT	25-28 July 2016	Austin, Texas	http://www.ask4research.info/icalt/2016/
ASME IDETC/CIE	21-25 Aug 2016	Charlotte, NC	https://www.asme.org/events/idetccie
IEEE Conference on Computational Intelligence and Games	20-23 Sep 2016	Santorini, Greece	http://cig16.image.ece.ntua.gr/
ECTEL 2016	13-15 Sep 2016	Paris, France	http://www.ec-tel.eu/index.php?id=732
VS Games	7-9 Sep 2016	Barcelona, Spain	http://vsgames2016.com/

ECGBL 2016	6-7 Oct 2016	Paisley, Scotland	http://www.academic-conferences.org/conferences/ecgbl/
Online Educa Berlin	30 Nov- 2 Dec 2016	Berlin, Germany	http://www.online-educa.com/
GALA/Serious Games Society Conference	5-7 Dec 2016	Utrecht, Netherlands	http://conf.seriousgamessociety.org/2016/
IGBL 2016	1-2 Sep 2016	Dublin, Ireland	http://www.igbl-conference.com/
IFIP ICEC 2016	28-30 Sep 2016	Vienna, Austria	https://icec2016.cs.univie.ac.at/
Artificial Intelligence and Interactive Digital Entertainment	8-12 Oct 2016	Burlingame, CA	http://www.aiide.org/
SGAMES 2016	16-17 June 2016	Porto, Portugal	http://sgamesconf.org/
ICWL 2016	26-29 Oct 2016	Rome, Italy	http://icwl2016.dis.uniroma1.it/
GALA 2016	5-7 Dec 2016	Utrecht, NL	http://conf.seriousgamessociety.org/2016

Table 4. List of relevant international conferences

This list only reflects the international conferences that have been considered more relevant for the BEACONING project. Most of the conferences mentioned in the table take place annually and many of the partners are already participating in them (e.g. PC committee, invited speaker, organiser, ...). Therefore by participating in these conferences the WP2 leader and the project coordinator will also actively promote and disseminate the BEACONING project development and results.

Additionally, each partner will be asked to identify and share with the rest of the consortium the national conferences and events that should be attended in order to adequately reach all national stakeholders.

Participation with scientific communities (institutes, universities, etc)

These will be able to expand their contributions to technology transfer and thus wider innovation by exposing their R&D breakthroughs across a new breed of demonstrators (e.g. Living labs) and experimentation sites, empowered by realistic arrays of serious games resources and services provided through the BEACONING infrastructure.

Here the idea is again to build upon the pre-existing formal and informal communities where the project partners are already active, and trying to use them as specialized channels for project dissemination.

Keynote presentations and invited conferences

There are several team members, mainly from the academic partners, that participate regularly in keynote presentations or invited conferences. These are ideal vehicles for creating awareness of the BEACONING project and later on for dissemination of its results, not only to the academic community but also to the game industry.

The project will promote these activities also for the game technology partners and the content providers, promoting their participation in the applied games, content education conferences, or professional meetings. We will actively promote the collaboration among industrial partners, so the presence of the BEACONING project could be relevant in those kinds of venues.

4.3 FACE TO FACE ACTIVITIES

"On-site" visits

When approaching local or regional authorities, as well as corporate third parties, a more proactive approach is required. As part of the BEACONING Dissemination effort, we expect to organize on-site visits to key stakeholder institutions, in order to capture their interest in the results of the project and promote their direct application.

An on-site visit allows the assigned BEACONING team to create relationships that cannot be adequately achieved through writing. On-site visits are conducted to reach more personal interactions between partners and stakeholders.

Contact with related EU projects

The H2020 Programme is well underway, and there is already a network of related projects that BEACONING should regularly align with in order to disseminate our results and exploit potential synergies with them (see Figure 1). By promoting the collaboration with other EU projects with a related topic, BEACONING project will both benefit of sharing knowledge on the same area, and increase its target population.

This goal will be achieved firstly through partners involved in other H2020 projects, and then through the expansion of the network by following up on further H2020 calls. In particular, the Commission expects (and BEACONING aspires to) regular communication across all projects related to educational technologies in general and gaming and gamification in particular.

Initial contacts and meetings with the RAGE project (Realising an Applied Gaming Ecosystem) have already been established (in June 2016), and are expected to remain strong due to the participation of some BEACONING partners also being involved in the RAGE project. We will extend this type of collaboration to other projects—even those not directly related with games—that involve technologies that could be relevant for BEACONING (e.g. LACE project, where learning analytics is a key supporting technology).

Figure 1: Establishing a network of Educational and Game-related H2020 projects
(source: RAGE project)

Visiting existing events of the stakeholders

The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) articulates a multitude of action channels such as participation to and organisation of events, direct contact, mass-media, online presence, and actively engagement of stakeholders.

Another approach for the dissemination of the project and its results is to proactively visit events organized by relevant stakeholders (institutional, academic or corporate), in order to engage with them in the promotion and exploitation of BEACONING's results. As argued above, stakeholders (industry, research and end-users) are key to the project's success, and guaranteeing the maximum impact among them should be one its priorities. That is why both dissemination partners and stakeholders, will be actively involved in the validation of the specific dissemination plans and activities.

4.4 OTHER ACTIONS AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Exhibits

Exhibiting BEACONING outcomes will help to improve both the motivation of its members to strive to the project (since they see tangible outcomes), and the perception of the stakeholders on what the project is achieving.

Among these events, we will emphasize success stories. As BEACONING evolves, the website will reflect success stories in a special section. Whenever a partner develops a case study or success story, it will be notified to the dissemination committee for approval. Once approved, it will be published on the Website. Benefits for the project will be twofold:

- 1) *Inside the consortium.* Partners' engagement will improve if they feel part of a real success story. In addition, the stories will foster feedback among the partners.
- 2) *Outside the consortium.* Success stories will help to raise stakeholders' awareness and interest towards the project.

Project partners' experience indicates that prominently displaying outcomes provides visitors with pertinent information about ongoing projects, and even encourages them to participate, and can foster discussion groups regarding displayed outcomes. As there is no specific budget for these activities in the project, we will try to use the partners' budget and to link them with other dissemination activities (e.g. participation in conferences)

Press/Broadcast

The main project milestones will be reported through general and localized press releases for maximum impact across the general population. These press releases will take three main approaches:

1. General centralized press releases, to be circulated as a uniform resource across different venues.
2. Customized press releases drafted from WP2 but sent to the partners to be individualised to their specific networks (language, highlights, etc.) in order to maximize local relevance and impact.
3. Independent partner-specific press releases. As there is a diversity of partners and countries involved in the project, we will try to achieve impact by writing in local journals and newspapers (in the local language), and by targeting local stakeholders.

For non-centralized press-releases we will opt for an agile low-burden approach, where partners will be free to generate or individualise press releases. Instead of seeking pre-approval, the only requisite will be to inform WP2, so that all press releases can be archived and reported in the BEACONING website.

Video Content

Video content is increasingly important; both to make the content more accessible and attractive to different kinds of public and to achieve presence in video-oriented social media such as YouTube. In BEACONING, we are considering two different kinds of video content. On the one hand, promotional videos will be created at different stages of the BEACONING project, and disseminated through the BEACONING website and using the project channel in the YouTube platform. On the other hand, we will create short interviews and other kinds of longer content (e.g. talks and presentation) with experts from the consortium and other third-party experts in the field (this strategy has already proven effective in other EU projects such as the LACE project). The availability of the YouTube channel allows also for the live-streaming of talks and presentation if required.

Flyers, brochures, etc.

For more effective dissemination, BEACONING will produce specific materials to facilitate communication of the project's concept, activities, benefits and outcomes.

The dissemination materials will be available in a digital format to print/share when needed and will be updated with recent findings or with other relevant information. In particular, we foresee the production of

- a) Branding and logotype material
- b) Flyers
- c) Project poster
- d) Press releases
- e) Official project slides

Following the same lean decentralized approach, each project partner will be able to adapt the content to their language and specific area or application simplifying the access and impact in their sector or locality (region/country).

Community Building

All BEACONING partners will aim to build a stable community that allows sharing ideas, materials, and speeding up the communication. It is our belief that building a community for supporting networking activities could help to cutting across the research/business/practitioners frontier. Therefore, BEACONING partners should promote the projects outcomes as well as its activities to engage non-BEACONING actors into our community.

The main instruments that will help to create and to foster the community are:

- a) Website.
- b) Newsletters.
- c) Conferences, seminars and events.
- d) Social Networks.

License for the dissemination content

In order to increase dissemination whenever it is possible, and unless explicitly stated, the default license for all the dissemination content will be Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.5 Generic (CC BY-SA 2.5) (more information about this license can be found at <https://creativecommons.org/>).

5 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPI)

To quantify the quality of the dissemination activities and achievements, a number of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be defined to serve as a reference during the project's lifetime. The main goal of these KPIs will be to measure and track the impact of project outcomes.

The impact of the different dissemination and communication activities will be followed up for each reporting period, in order to detect the relative success of each activity and to foster further efforts when required.

In particular, we identify the following Key Performance Indicators, and propose specific targets to benchmark the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication effort.

It should be noted that most of the M7 key performance indicators have been already met so we can consider that the project is clearly on track.

5.1 DIGITAL COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Project website

KPIs identified include the number of hits to the BEACONING website, the number of unique visitors and the number of external links pointing to the website.

Website KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Page hits	500	5000	10000	30000	60000
Unique visitors	20	300	500	2000	4000
Incoming links	14	37	47	67	100
Countries made aware	10	15	25	50	60

Table 5. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING Website

Also, the website is monitored on a monthly basis using Google Analytics and Hootsuite Intelligence to identify website's visits, unique visitors, time per visit, traffic source and other key metrics that will track visitors' experience and engagement. External indices such as Alexa Rank or Google Rank could give us additional insights on the website success.

Social media

Social media impact will be measured through standard metrics, including the number of posts, the number of subscribers, and the exposure of the accounts. Besides, external indexes could help to get measurements that are more accurate. For example, Klout Score yields a number in the range from 1 to 100 that represents social network influence.

Social Media KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of posts	10	50	100	200	300
Number of subscribers	30	200	500	750	1000
Interactions (FB Likes, Twitter Retweet, Share, etc.)	20	100	200	400	600
Reach (prints, visits, etc.)	500	5000	10000	50000	75000

Table 6. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING Social Media channels

The following table shows the description of different metrics that will be used for the most important social networks.

Platform	KPI	Description
Twitter	Tweets	Total number of tweets published in a defined period of time.
	Engagement rate	The percentage of total number of engagements (clicks, retweets, favourites, etc.) divided by total impressions.
	Retweets	Total number of users who have Re-tweeted (RT) BEACONING's tweet in a defined period. A Retweet is a re-posting of someone else's Tweet.
	Followers	Total number of users who have clicked the "follow" button on BEACONING's twitter page
LinkedIn	Discussions	Total number of publications posted at LinkedIn Group Discussions in a period defined
	Members	Total number of users who have joined the LinkedIn Group in a period defined
Google+	Followers	Total number of users who have clicked the "follow" button on BEACONING's Google+ page
	Visits	Total number of visitors in a period of time defined
Blog	News	Total number of posts (news) published in a period defined
	Page views	Total number of pages printed/views in a period defined
	Unique page views	Total number of pages printed/view by visitors the first time in a period defined

Table 7. Description of metrics per platform.

Newsletters

The newsletter is a very straightforward mechanism, and will be measured in terms of messages sent and number of subscribers. We expect a quarterly publication schedule beginning on month 6 of the project.

Newsletter KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of posts	1	3	4	6	10
Number of subscribers	100	200	250	600	1000

Table 8. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING Social Media channels

5.2 ACADEMIC ACTIVITIES

Number and impact factor of academic publications, conference contributions and keynote contributions.

Scientific papers, Conferences, Newspaper articles, etc.

The academic partners in BEACONING are expected to maintain an important presence in academic dissemination venues, and the following KPIs are established:

Publication KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Conference papers		9	15	25	30
Journal papers		1	2	8	12
Newspaper articles	1	3	4	5	10
Books				1	

Table 9. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING academic papers

Conferences, seminars, workshops

The participation in academic events will be measured in terms of number of events and their global audience.

Workshop KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of posts		7	7	9	18
Number of attendants (each region)		50		100	150

Table 10. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING workshops

Keynote presentations and Lectures

Keynote presentations and invited lectures will be measured cumulatively in terms of number of events and accumulated audience size.

Keynotes and conferences KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of events	3	15	25	40	50
Number of attendants (cumulative)	60	300	500	800	1000

Table 11. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING participation in keynotes and conferences

5.3 FACE TO FACE ACTIVITIES

"On-site" visits and stakeholder involvement

The effect of all direct stakeholder outreach activities will be measured in aggregation through the number of stakeholders involved with the project.

Stakeholder involvement KPIs	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of industrial partners	5	10	25	30	50
Number of end-user intermediaries	4	10	25	30	50
Number of research organizations	7	10	25	30	50
Number of interviews (industry-level)		10		30	
Number of focus groups	14	20	30	50	

Table 12. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING stakeholder involvement

Contact with related EU projects

[Details about this activity]

Project networking KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of events	3	15	25	40	50
Number of attendants (cumulative)	60	300	500	800	1000

Table 13. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING keynotes and conferences

5.4 OTHER ACTIONS AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Whenever possible project partners will be advised to provide indicators (e.g. numbers) that measure the dissemination activity taking into account very different factors. Here it is not so simple to provide clear KPIs as in many cases there is not a contrasted way to measure those actions.

Exhibits

The number of attendees to BEACONING exhibits could provide insight into the channel's effectiveness. Depending on the exhibit, it could also reflect the effectiveness of the dissemination plan as a whole, and the impact that other channels have in the community.

Press/Broadcast

The press release strategy is mostly focused on the individual actions of partners to achieve an impact in their local communities; the indicators will be measured in terms of the impact factor of those particular efforts. In this sense, the capacity and the efforts of each partner to garner press coverage in their countries and cities will be key to achieve greater impact.

On the other hand, the number of viewers for broadcasted contents will provide a yardstick for success in this kind of media.

Promotional videos

As explained above, promotional videos rely on success by the number of viewers. Whenever promotional videos are launched in non-Youtube based platforms, they should include a mechanism to measure the number of views they receive.

Flyers, Brochures and Broadcast/Press Magazines

These actions themselves are not an end. However, we have learnt from publicity campaigns that the number of produced materials of this kind will have a direct impact on the rest of performance indicators. Therefore, it seems reasonable to expect that the more materials produced the more impact achieved in other channels (such as exhibits, social networks or newsletters subscribers). Still, we are aware that the decentralized model followed in this intervention will make any direct measure of its outcomes difficult.

Community Building

Social media dissemination efforts will ensure an interesting outcome in terms of discussions, consultations, feedback and content sharing and engagement. As the instruments to build up the community will be the website, newsletters, conferences and social networks, the general measurement of the community impact will be the result of the impact in those mediums (described in each section).

In addition, we will consider that sometimes the impact takes longer than just an immediate reaction (e.g. in EU policy making, Exploitation Plan, etc.). Therefore, it is quite possible that the seeds scattered at the beginning of the community building will be harvested much later. This will be considered when monitoring the global impact of the project.

6 VISUAL IDENTITY AND BRANDING: LOGOS, OFFICIAL PRESENTATIONS AND TEMPLATES

To ensure the success in taking-up the BEACONING results, the focus of the project’s dissemination and communication efforts should target the entire Educational Value Chain and should create an easy recognizable identity with a very distinctive visual branding.

The main elements of the visual brand are the logos (in long and short versions), the official presentations (including a power point and a project brochure), press releases, and the different project official document templates (i.e. Microsoft Word and Microsoft Powerpoint templates). These templates will allow an easy-to-recognize visual branding of all the documents created by each project member, and facilitate the adaptation to specific local requirements and languages.

All those elements of the visual branding and the first version of the official documents will be available in the first three months of the project from the official website (we do not repeat them here). A full description of the visual identity can be found in deliverable D2.2 Project branding and website start-up.

Figure 2. BEACONING visual identity including logos and icons